

METHODS FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' READING LITERACY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *The ultimate goal of teaching reading literacy is to enable students to derive meaning from text. That is, during reading, students should be able to generate new meanings, conclusions, and understandings regarding ideas or information that are not explicitly stated. Indeed, texts—regardless of genre or type—are created with the intention that readers draw specific conclusions. A student's ability to fully understand the meaning and content of a text depends on several components, where the teacher's active role becomes crucial.*

Keywords: *persistent disinterest, reading literacy, text comprehension, innovative progress.*

Introduction. Due to difficulties in reading, students often develop a persistent disinterest in reading, which affects their overall development. In such situations, special attention and control are necessary. While all students develop reading skills, not all of them equally acquire the ability to comprehend what they read. This highlights the importance of wisely selecting effective methods and tools to teach reading and text comprehension, as emphasized by M. Asqarova in her dissertation on developing reading and text comprehension skills in primary school students.

The process of improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers to enhance students' reading literacy is also carried out based on official educational standards, curricula, and syllabi. The goal of education based on these programs is to enhance the methodological training of future primary school teachers in developing students' reading literacy. This continuous process requires a systematic and consistent approach.

In this context, subjects taught in higher education play an important role in the methodological training of future teachers. Currently, it is necessary to enrich educational and methodological resources and determine innovative approaches in the implementation of updated curricula and programs for training future primary school teachers. New programs are being developed to improve modern education and schools.

The subject "International Assessment Programs in Primary Education," taught to students specializing in primary education, serves as a key source in enhancing the methodological preparation of future teachers to develop students' reading literacy. In addition to improving methodological training, this subject emphasizes the importance of the PIRLS international study and the need to teach it to students [5].

In a rapidly developing era of innovative progress, it is crucial to support the creative ideas and innovation of youth—our future—and to shape their knowledge, skills, and competencies. It is also important to study and adopt advanced foreign experiences, improve assessment systems based on international standards and requirements, and closely collaborate with international organizations and research institutions. For over 60 years, the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) has led comparative studies in education,

evaluating the impact of state policies and practices on education through large-scale research. These studies analyze educational processes and outcomes, and identify factors affecting education quality through comparative analysis.

These studies are conducted at a high technical level and in accordance with scientific standards. Depending on the nature of the cases being studied, practical methods such as observation are also used effectively.

The “Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS)” is a major international assessment program that measures the reading comprehension skills of 4th-grade students. It provides data for comparing reading literacy levels worldwide and offers insights to inform educational policies and improve teaching and learning.

In addition to evaluating reading comprehension, PIRLS also assesses students’ literary experiences, ability to process information, and literacy in using information effectively.

According to Presidential Decree PF-5712, dated April 29, 2019, on the approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, Uzbekistan aims to rank among the top 30 countries in the PISA international program by 2030. The decree also emphasizes establishing a national education quality assessment system focused on reading, mathematics, and science literacy [3].

Building a student-centered educational process requires special attention to content and should include the following essential components: axiological, cognitive, activity-creative, and personal.

The foundations of the student-centered approach have been studied by I.S. Yakimanskaya, A.K. Markova, V.V. Serikov, and I.A. Zimnyaya. They interpret this approach as the acquisition of personal qualities by individuals through their life activities. The essence of personality-oriented education lies in enabling learners to fulfill personal responsibilities.

Implementing a personality-oriented approach involves not only considering students’ individual psychological traits but also the development of cognition, personal qualities, and characteristics of activity. The axiological approach is extensively studied in the research process. In addition to other scientific methods, the axiological approach plays a significant role in understanding reality. Scientific cognition examines how values are reflected in human consciousness, the laws and levels of understanding values, and the criteria and norms of such understanding. This relies not only on general epistemology but also on data from social and natural sciences, particularly evidence from intellectual activity, logic, and linguistics [2].

M. Urazova studied the interaction between the pedagogical process and its subjects, and the positive aspects of using axiological approaches. When evaluating a specific period or historical stage using an axiological approach, attention is paid to how it differs from other eras in terms of social significance, value, and uniqueness. The achievements, historical contributions, legacy, and relevance of a period are taken into account.

In the axiological approach, education must be directed toward the values of society, its functions, relationships, culture, and personality.

In the model for improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers in developing students’ reading literacy, educational principles such as humanism and systemicity are applied.

These principles help resolve pedagogical contradictions. If future primary teachers do not understand their importance and necessity, success in organizing research activities is unlikely. Therefore, appropriate methodological preparation of students is essential.

The humanization principle of the educational process implies that future teachers and their research supervisors take full responsibility for the quality and timing of research projects. Humanization also involves delegating part of the responsibility for scientific and experimental research results to the student.

The principle of humanizing the pedagogical process includes the use of psychological and pedagogical technologies that instill humanistic attitudes in students. Personality-oriented relationships aim to develop defining qualities of individuals, such as:

- a) collaborative creativity with future primary teachers: mutual understanding, communication, support, consistency, openness, listening skills, and more;
- b) positive self-perception: goal orientation, efficiency, determination, responsibility, awareness of decisions made, accountability for actions, etc.;
- c) legal compliance: responsibility, clarity, politeness, independence, assertiveness, self-control, and self-correction.

The main idea of the principle of systemicity, as reflected in the works of V.I. Andreev, Yu.K. Babansky, V.K. Buryak, S.M. Markova, and V.A. Slastenin, is based on the uniqueness of interrelated components, which allows us to speak of a system. In this case, a system is understood as any object and the elements of a larger system encompassing it.

Stage	Content	Activities to be Implemented
Motivation	Developing students' interest and need for effectively using resources	Explaining the importance of mastering reading literacy in both educational and real-life contexts to develop students' interest and needs.
Cognitive	Developing the ability to independently analyze studied sources	Explaining the essential concepts of the subject 'Reading Literacy' based on understanding their meaning and essence.
Creative	Forming a creative approach while working with texts in the reading literacy textbook	Improving factors that generate creative approaches, such as the ability to evaluate situations and propose necessary assumptions in both standard and non-standard situations across subject areas.

Motivational Stage. Improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers to develop students' reading literacy serves as the foundation for the motivational stage, which aims to foster learners' interest in and need for effectively using various informational sources. Through enhancing the methodological preparedness of future primary school teachers, students are expected to understand the practical relevance of newly acquired knowledge, both in educational materials and in real-life activities.

At this stage, students' awareness of the importance of reading materials leads to their motivation to engage in the learning process. Moreover, this encourages students to perceive learning as a meaningful activity aligned with real-life contexts. The informational content

presented as part of instructional materials also contributes to evaluating the quality of education and developing effective methodological support.

During the motivational stage, learners begin to participate in educational activities with conscious involvement, adapting to the new conditions and approaches in education.

Cognitive Stage. The cognitive stage emphasizes the use of modern and effective teaching methods that align with current educational requirements and technological advancements. It is necessary to ensure harmony between teachers and students with the evolving demands of the time.

Students must develop a full understanding of self-management in a modern, information-rich society. This stage focuses on enabling learners to grasp the theoretical foundations and core concepts needed to acquire new knowledge during reading literacy lessons. It also aims to activate information consumption culture and ensure students' successful adaptation to the realities of an information-based society[1].

Instructional materials selected for this stage are based on these goals and support the development of students' comprehension skills. They help students navigate and understand key ideas, enhance critical thinking, and build the competencies needed for lifelong learning.

Creative Stage. The creative stage involves cultivating creativity in both learners and educators by enabling the application of reading literacy-related concepts and terminology. In this phase, future primary school teachers are encouraged to not only comprehend and convey information but also solve problems, analyze learning situations, and propose reasonable assumptions or hypotheses.

This process requires both teachers and students to exhibit creativity, particularly when working with reading literacy content. Learners must engage in tasks that involve evaluation, problem-solving, and the creation of new ideas. Educators, in turn, are expected to foster an environment that supports imaginative thinking and flexible application of methodological tools.

Factors Contributing to the Emergence of Creative Approaches in the Process of Improving the Methodological Training of Future Primary School Teachers in Developing Students' Reading Literacy.

Individual Characteristics of the Personality: The ability to evaluate unusual and ambiguous situations, adapt effectively, and choose the most appropriate solutions; flexibility and diversity in expressed thoughts; and the capacity to periodically break out of one's "comfort zone" are crucial factors that facilitate the development of a creative approach in teachers.

Creative Environment. A consistently supportive environment that encourages creativity, and the presence of various factors that contribute to its formation, are essential. This includes stimuli that create "explosive" or breakthrough effects—conditions that spark creativity within a group of learners. Such an environment fosters creative thinking and expression among students and supports the methodological development of the teacher[2].

The operational block of the model encompasses the forms, methods, and means of instruction used to enhance the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers in fostering students' reading literacy. The curriculum for the Reading Literacy subject in primary grades should not only focus on content but also ensure the effective organization of learning materials to create optimal conditions for conceptual generalization.

Conclusion. Analysis reveals that the curriculum for Reading Literacy in primary school is structured with both visual and textual materials presented in a logical sequence. This structured

layout facilitates the comprehension and integration of educational content, aligning with pedagogical objectives and supporting effective methodological application by teachers.

REFERENCES

1. Maslou A. Motivatsiya i lichnost (Motivation and Personality). – SPb.: Piter, 2003. – 200 s.
2. Abdulazizov A. Akademik litsey va kasb-xunar kollejarida mutolaa madaniyatini shakllantirish jarayonining sotsiologik taxlili: sos.fan.nom. ... diss. Avtoref. – T.: 2010. – 30 b.
3. Olofsson A. Thresholds of Interpretation. Cambridge: CUP, 1997.– P.453.
4. W. Li, Sh. Kang, Y. Shao, Development of the reading literacy questionnaire for EFL learners at primary schools. 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1154076
5. E .Kennedy, E. Dunphy, B Dwyer, Literacy in Early Childhood and Primary Education. <http://www.ncca.ie>